

5 ERTEXT MODELING TOOL PROPOSAL

This chapter presents the main proposal of this study. Aspects about the definition of DSL are detailed, as well as the modeling tool built.

5.1 Development

The development of the modeling tool proposal took place from the work extension of (LOPES, 2019), restarting from June 2020. In that study, we have defined language requirements, design decisions, and derived grammar. We use all these concepts to implement the new editor infrastructure that supports this DSL.

5.1.1 Language Requirements

This section lists the requirements defined based on the literature used in this work and even the prior knowledge of the researchers involved in conducting the study. These requirements are directly related to design decisions.

- ***RQ1. The DSL must be made available under an open-source license.*** As the focus of the proposal is on the teaching process, the language must be open-source. The advantage that this requirement provides is the further evolution and collaborative maintenance with the involvement of other developers.
- ***RQ2. The DSL must allow the textual representation of conceptual DB models.*** As it is an objective that the solution is another option concerning graphical approaches, this requirement is justified. This allows focusing on understanding the domain and developing the DSL.
- ***RQ3. The conceptual models must support the definition of entities, attributes, relationships, and cardinalities.*** The tool used to develop the language needs to allow implementation of the domain concepts that govern the traditional ER diagram structure.
- ***RQ4. The conceptual models must support the definition of identifying attributes, generalization/specialization, self-relationships, and ternary relationships.*** The language should allow more sophisticated domain concepts to be defined.
- ***RQ5. The implementation of DSL must perform the transformation from the conceptual to the logical model.*** The solution must perform the transformation from conceptual to logical, displaying the generated result to the user.

- **RQ6. The implementation of DSL must generate equivalent SQL statements based on the conceptual or logical model.** The solution needs to generate SQL statements for different DBMSs.
- **RQ7. The implementation of DSL should generate some form of graphical representation.** The solution needs to perform diagram generation based on the conceptual model.

5.1.2 Design Decisions

This section describes the Design Decisions (DD) to create the textual DSL that supports all the requirements presented in Section 5.1.1.

For each design decision, we have indicated its associated requirements.

- **DD1. The solution should adopt an open-source LW to help implement the textual DSL (RQ1, RQ2).** Through the investigation conducted in the previously cited study (LOPES, 2019), we have selected LW Xtext for the development of the proposal as it is an open-source framework focused on the development of textual DSLs, providing all the necessary infrastructure. Furthermore, Xtext is a tool with a high level of maturity, detailed documentation and an extremely active community.
- **DD2. The DSL must provide a textual representation equivalent to the commonly used graphical ER models (RQ3, RQ4).** For the requirements covered by this design decision, we have adopted the strategy of performing an analysis in the tools verified in the mapping described in (LOPES, 2019), as well as in the reference book by (HEUSER, 2009).
- **DD3. The solution must perform the transformation between models (RQ5).** Xtext uses Eclipse Modeling Framework (EMF) templates as the in-memory representation of any parsed text file. This in-memory object graph is called an Abstract Syntax Tree (AST). These concepts are also called Document Object Graph (DOM), semantic model, or simply model. Thus, there is a representation of the grammar model in the form of a kernel metamodel in the core of EMF, called the Ecore model. Since having the proposed DSL Ecore as a representation, it is possible to apply transformation rules, thus generating other models.
- **DD4. The solution must provide the integration between the DSL and other technologies (RQ6).** The solution should allow the export of the built models to an SQL statement format, thus representing the physical model. Initially we perform this integration for PostgreSQL and MySQL

- **DD5.** *The solution should provide the generation and visualization of diagrams of the models built with DSL (RQ7).* The solution must allow the visualization of data models built using a graphical format and representing the conceptual model. Initially we perform this integration using PlantUML. PlantUML is an open-source tool that allows the creation of diagrams from a simple text language.

5.1.3 DSL Grammar

In the current phase of the work, the language at the conceptual level is meeting the language requirements defined in Section 5.1.1. The definition of DSL using a variation of the Extended Backus-Naur Form (EBNF) metasyntax notation is displayed in Figure 9.

Figure 9 – Definition of implemented DSL grammar.

```

grammar org.xtext.unipampa.erdsl.ErDsl with org.eclipse.xtext.common.Terminals
generate erDsl "http://www.xtext.org/unipampa/erdsl/ErDsl"

ERModel:
  ("Generate" targetGenerator= ("LogicalSchema" | "PostgreSQL" |
                                "MySQL" | "Diagram" | "All") ";" )?
  domain=Domain ";"
  ("Entities" "{" entities+=Entity+ ("}" ";" )
  ("Relationships" "{" relations+=Relation* ("}" ";" );

Domain:
  "Domain" name=ID;

Attribute:
  name=ID type=DataType (iskey?="isIdentifier")?;

Entity:
  name=ID ("is" generalization=("total/disjoint" | "total/overlapped" |
                                "partial/disjoint" | "partial/overlapped")
  is=[Entity]?
  ("{" attributes+=Attribute
  ("," attributes+=Attribute)* "}")?;

Relation:
  (name=ID) ("[" leftEnding=RelationSideLeft
  "relates"
  rightEnding=RelationSideRight "]" )
  ("{" attributes+=Attribute
  ("," attributes+=Attribute)* "}")*;

RelationSideLeft:
  target=[Entity] | target=[Relation]
  cardinality=("0:1" | "1:1" | "0:N" | "1:N") ;

RelationSideRight:
  cardinality=("0:1" | "1:1" | "0:N" | "1:N")
  target=[Entity] | target=[Relation];

enum DataType:
  INT="int" | DOUBLE="double" | MONEY="money" | STRING="string" |
  BOOLEAN="boolean" | DATETIME="datetime" | BLOB="file";

```

Source – Author.

There are topics related to scope validation that we analyzed and then imple-